

NANOCLAY EXFOLIATION PROCESS FOR EPOXY/ORGANOCLAY NANOCOMPOSITES: EFFECT OF EPOXY REACTIVE DILUENTS AND DIAMINE CURING AGENTS

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1 Introduction

The investigation of organically modified layered silicates has opened a totally new window for the development of polymer matrix composites with excellent properties and applications. These modified plastic systems are called Polymer-Layered Silicate Nanocomposites (PLSNs). PLSNs are known to have unexpected properties, e.g. mechanical, thermal and barrier properties.

Toyota Motor Company developed a breakthrough clay nanocomposite of polyamine 6 and polyamine 6/66 copolymer for structural applications [1-2]. By replacing naturally Na⁺ and Ca⁺ exchange cations of pristine clay with a more hydrophobic organic onium ion, they were able to intercalate and polymerize in the clay gallery region to form a nylon-exfoliated clay hybrid composite. The modulus was raised by 40%, the strength was increased by 50% and the heat distortion temperature is increased by 80 °C compared with the pristine polymer.

Unitika Ltd. of Japan [3] developed polyamine 6 nanocomposite (Nylon M2350) using synthetic clay as reinforcement during polymerization. Nylon M2350 has been used by Mitsubishi Motors for an engine cover on its GDI models, where the nanocomposite is said to offer a 20% weight reduction and excellent surface finish. Kojima *et al.* [4] studied the mechanical properties of polyamine 6-clay nanocomposites prepared using organically modified montmorillonite and synthetic clays. TEM showed that both nanocomposites were exfoliated. The polyamine 6-clay composite (PACC) was superior in strength and modulus to nylon 6. The flexural strength of PACH at 120 °C was double than that of polyamine 6. The flexural and tensile modulus was 4 times and 3 times that of polyamine 6 respectively.

The enhancement of barrier properties is believed to depend on the degree of exfoliation of the clay platelets. In the fully exfoliated state, individual clay platelets have the highest aspect ratio possible and thus the highest barrier improvement is expected. Kojima *et al.* [5] studied the barrier of polyamine-montmorillonite and polyamine-saponite (synthetic clay) nanocomposites to water. Both polyamine-montmorillonite and polyamine-saponite nanocomposites had better barrier to water than nylon homopolymer. The higher aspect ratio of montmorillonite compared to saponite, it clearly that polyamine-montmorillonite nanocomposites were better barrier property to water than polyamine-saponite nanocomposites.

Most of the studies explained above have related the property enhancement to the dispersion and/or the aspect ratio of the clay platelets. Properties mentioned above depend on the transport of some material in and out of the sample and thus, the enhancement in these properties will depend on the orientation of the clay platelets in the sample. For this reason recent studies have proposed that along with the dispersion.

One of the most common nano-fillers is montmorillonite (MMT). Generally, untreated clays are not applied for nanocomposites and it is necessary to prepare organoclays, which are incorporated organic cations via cation exchange reaction. Then, it becomes possible for nanocomposites to improve the affinity between the clay and polymer. Several PLSNs have successfully been prepared using organically modified montmorillonite (OMMT) with polyamine as the most successful matrix [6-10]. In the field of thermosetting polymers, polymer/clay nanocomposites have been not yet industrialized.

However, the improvement of various properties has been reported about the epoxy/clay nanocomposites by ammonium modified clay in many reports [11-14]. Kornmann *et al.*[15-16] prepared the epoxy resins filled with various amine modifiers and showed the morphologies and thermal, mechanical properties influenced with the addition of amine modifiers on the organoclays. They reported the enhancements of flexural modulus and fracture properties on nanocomposites

In the case of MMT, this is commonly achieved by treating it with large organic surfactants, usually ammonium ions. In their natural state, the MMT layers have a net negative charge and are held together by electrostatic forces between the sheets and interlaying inorganic cations. These ions are effectively exchanged with the ammonium ions which penetrate the clay gallery and increase the distance between the sheets. The clay gets more or less hydrophobic depending on the exact structure of the ammonium ion tails.

To a great extent the outcome relies on the processing technique used. PLSNs can be made either by adding the filler in the polymerisation step, in a solution or straight into a polymer melt. The latter is very attractive due to its simplicity; existing machinery and procedures can be used. The result is, however, strongly affected by parameters such as shear forces, processing time, temperature, etc. as shown in several studies [17-18]. The impact of these parameters also depends on the polymer matrix used.

Epoxy resin has been of significant importance to the engineering community for many years. Components made of epoxy-based materials have provided outstanding mechanical and thermal properties as well as chemical stabilities. Many attempts have been made so far to use epoxy as the matrix, however, only few have fully succeeded.

Clay dispersion methods and corrosion behavior of epoxy/organoclay nanocomposites in our previous study [19] showed that high speed mixing plays an important role on clay dispersion. Epoxy/organoclay nanocomposite via high speed mixing method performed better corrosion resistant compared to propeller and three-roll calendar mixing method, however, still have a challenge on homogeneous clay dispersion in the epoxy matrix.

The pre-mixing substances are designed to various functional groups (epoxy and amine functional groups which are compatibility with epoxy resins and ability for the curing accelerator) and different size of molecular chain, which could be adaptable to interlayer spaces, and to investigate mechanical property and diffusion behavior of epoxy/organoclay nanocomposites. The aim of this study is to acquire fully exfoliated organoclay into epoxy matrix using pre-mixing substances as well as to investigate mechanical property and diffusion behavior of epoxy/organoclay nanocomposites.

2 Experimental Method

2.1 Materials

Commercially available diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A type epoxy (DGEBA), Epomik R140 was purchased from Mitsui Chemical Co., Ltd. used as matrix, which had an epoxide equivalent weight of 188 g/equiv. Diamine curing agent, Jeffamine D230 produced from Huntsman Corporation was used as curing agent. Figure 1 shows the structures of the materials used in this study. Montmorillonite-based organoclay (Nanomer I.30E) from Nanocor Inc., was used in this study to produce the nanocomposites. Nanomer I.30E nanoclays are surface compatibilized montmorillonites. In addition to traditional inner gallery cation exchange modification, Nanomer I.30E uses n-octadecyl ammonium as treatment agent as shown in Fig. 2 and surface modifier concentration is 28-32 mass%

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of materials used in this study.

Fig. 2. Chemical structures of n-octadecyl ammonium

Pre-mixing substances employed in this study were selected two functional groups with two variants. First pre-mixing substance is epoxy reactive diluents (EPICLON 703 and EPICLON 720, short and long molecular structure, respectively), and the other pre-

Table 1 Structures of pre-mixing substances.

Abbreviation of Pre-mixing substance	Commercial name	Chemical structure
E1	EPICLON 703	$\text{R-O-CH}_2\text{-HC}\begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \text{---} \end{array}\text{CH}_2$ <p>R: C12-C13</p>
E2	EPICLON 720	$\text{H}_2\text{C}\begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \text{---} \end{array}\text{CH-H}_2\text{C-O-H}_2\text{C-C}\begin{array}{c} \text{CH}_3 \\ \\ \text{---} \\ \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array}\text{-CH}_2\text{-O-CH}_2\text{-HC}\begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \text{---} \end{array}\text{CH}_2$
D1	D400	$\text{H}_2\text{N}\left(\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}\begin{array}{c} \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array}\text{-O}\right)_x\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}\begin{array}{c} \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array}\text{-NH}_2$ <p style="text-align: right;">X≈6.1</p>
D2	D2000	$\text{H}_2\text{N}\left(\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}\begin{array}{c} \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array}\text{-O}\right)_x\text{CH}_2\text{-CH}\begin{array}{c} \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{array}\text{-NH}_2$ <p style="text-align: right;">X≈33</p>

mixing substance is diamine curing agents (D400 and D2000, short and long molecular structure, respectively). Table 1 shows the structures of the pre-mixing substances used in this study.

2.2 Method

Initially, to prepare organoclay/pre-mixing substance, pre-mixing substances were mixed with 10 mass% organoclay via high speed homogenizer (Ultra-TURRAX T18, IKA.) for 15 minutes, following by 15 minutes ultrasonic bath, and repeating both processes for 4 times. After that, the 10 mass% mixtures were mixed with epoxy via the homogenizer for 10 minutes. After mixing according to the above conditions, the mixtures were degassed under vacuum for 10 minutes. Thereafter, cooling down to room temperature, and then, epoxy resin and curing agent were added according to stoichiometric ratio to the mixtures stirred with degassing again for 10 minutes before casting. Finally, the organoclay/pre-mixing substance mixture of epoxy with diamine curing agent was cured at 80°C in oven for six hours and followed by post curing at 120°C in the oven for 12 hours.

2.3 Characterization

2.3.1 Clay Dispersion

2.3.1.1 Viscosity

To evaluate clay dispersion, viscosities of organoclay/pre-mixing substance suspensions after mixing process were measured at 25°C on Anton Paar – Physica MCR 100 viscometer using cone and plate geometry.

Fig.3. Typical rheology machine in this study

2.3.1.2 D – spacing

D-spacing of organoclay (OMMT) was measured using a Philips MRD X'Pert with a rotation anode and CuK α radiation (Å). The scanning range was from 1.05° to 9.95°. The step size was 0.02° and the step time was 3 sec for the measurement of the d-spacing. The d-spacing of different mixing conditions were investigated. For the analysis of the clay powder, particles were mounted on a sample holder with a large cavity and a smooth surface was obtained by passing the particles with a glass plate. Analysis of organoclay swollen in the epoxy resin with the curing agent was performed by placing the sample composites on the sample holder. The nanocomposite plates produced during the molding process had a fairly smooth surface which has been directly analyzed. The d-spacing was calculated according to Bragg's equation as following:

Fig.4. Schematic diagram of Bragg condition. When considering a wave incident on the parallel lattice planes path difference of waves reflected from surface adjacent becomes $2d\sin\theta$.

$$n\lambda = 2d\sin\theta \quad (1)$$

where n is intensity [Counts], λ is CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$) [\AA], d is interfacial distance or layer spacing (d -spacing) [\AA], and θ is angle [$^\circ$, degree]

2.3.1.3 Morphology

The nanoclay composite structure and clay distribution were examined using Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM). TEM images were obtained by a JEOL 2010F equipped with a field-emission gun operating at 200kV. TEM samples were prepared by ultramicrotome to be thin sections of the polymer nanocomposite with a diamond knife. These thin sections were then captured on coated Cu grids. The samples were tested at different magnifications from 2 μm to 200 nm scale bar.

2.4 Mechanical property

Flexural property was evaluated by three-point bending test using a bending machine according to ASTM D790. To study corrosion behavior of the nanocomposites, immersion test at 60°C under 10 mass% of sulfuric acid was selected to determine diffusivity and equilibrium mass change.

Fig.5. Size and shape of flexural tested specimen

2.5 Immersion Behavior

The immersion test specimens of $60 \times 25 \times 2 \text{ mm}^3$ for measurement of initial mass were dried at 50°C in oven for more than 75 hours. All specimens holding with a Teflon tube, in order to avoid sample overlapping, were tested in beaker containing 10% of sulfuric acid solution separately. The beakers were sealed with plastic film to avoid evaporation of the solution. The samples were performed in water bath controlled at 60°C according to the previous study [18]. Specimens were removed at regular time, washed by water and then carefully wiped to remove excess of acid on the specimens. The mass change was determined by obtaining the change in mass of specimen, relative to the initial mass and is calculated by,

$$M_t = \frac{W_t - W_0}{W_0} \times 100\%$$

Where M_t = Mass gain (%), W_0 = Initial mass of dry sample (g) and W_t = Mass of wet sample (g).

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Clay Dispersion

3.1.1 Viscosity

Fig. 6. % Change of viscosity of different pre-mixing substances with 10 mass% organoclay after mixing

Viscosity was selected as one parameter in this study to detect degree of clay exfoliation in clay/pre-mixing substance suspension. Fig. 6 and Table 2

shows viscosity and % change of neat pre-mixing substance and pre-mixing substance with 10 mass% organoclay after mixing with high speed homogenizer base on neat pre-mixing substances. As shown in Fig.6, pre-mixing substances significantly affected to increase viscosity. For epoxy functional group, small epoxy reactive diluent (E1) remarkably increase viscosity more than 7,400% after pre-mixing compared to neat E1 pre-mixing substances. For amine functional group, on the other hand, long molecular chain of diamine curing agents (D2) markedly increases viscosity after pre-mixing process. The result of viscosity can imply that pre-mixing substance is necessary in mixing process to obtain fully exfoliation PLSNs.

3.1.2 D – spacing

Fig. 7 shows XRD patterns of organoclay and epoxy/organoclay nanocomposites with various pre-mixing substances. The d-spacing or interlayer distance corresponding to the gap between clay layers is calculated according to Bragg's law. The pristine organoclay has a single sharp peak at $2\theta = 4.7^\circ$, which corresponds to d-spacing of 18.7 Å or 1.87 nm. For epoxy/organoclay nanocomposites with various pre-mixing substances, clear peaks are not detected. It implies that organoclay mixing appropriate pre-mixing substances successfully archive fully exfoliated clay structure in epoxy/clay nanocomposites.

More details on XRD result of epoxy/organoclay nanocomposites with different pre-mixing substances, XRD patterns of E1 and D2 pre-mixing substances observed shifts of diffraction peaks to not only smaller angles (It mean stretches of distances between the silicate layers of the organoclays), but also flatter in comparison with E2 and D1 pre-mixing substances, respectively. The XRD result was confirm that firstly pre-mixing substances help to obtain high degree of clay exfoliation in epoxy matrix, and secondly both XRD and viscosity proved that small molecular structure of epoxy reactive diluent and long molecular structure of diamine curing agent would obtain higher clay exfoliation on epoxy matrix compared to long molecular structure of epoxy reactive diluent and short molecular structure of diamine curing agent, respectively.

Fig. 7. XRD patterns of organoclay and epoxy/organoclay nanocomposites with various pre-mixing substances

3.1.3 Morphology

The structure and morphology of clay dispersion in nanocomposites were determined by TEM as shown in Fig. 8. TEM micrographs of epoxy/clay nanocomposites containing E1 and D2 pre-mixing substances are shown in Fig. 8(a,b) and Fig. 8(c,d), respectively. The dark lines on the bright-scattered images correspond to organoclay. The exfoliated and homogeneously dispersed silicate layers in both epoxy and diamine pre-mixing substances were obviously observed. The clay layers are more uniformly and exfoliatedly dispersed in the epoxy that was prepared with E1 compared to D2.

The increase in the exfoliation of the layered clay

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Table 2 Viscosity of neat pre-mixing substance and pre-mixing substance/organoclay after mixing process

Sample	Viscosity [Pa · s]	% Change of viscosity base on neat pre-mixing substance
E1	0.0083	-
E1/ Organoclay	0.61	7305
E2	0.02	-
E2/ Organoclay	0.20	749
D1	0.05	-
D1/ Organoclay	0.11	135
D2	0.39	-
D2/ Organoclay	4.38	1011

Fig. 8. TEM images of epoxy/clay/pre-mixing substance nanocomposites containing: epoxy/organoclay/E1 nanocomposite with (a) low and (b) magnification; epoxy/organoclay/D2 nanocomposite with (c) low and (d) high magnification

as shown in Fig 8a and b has a positive effect on the exfoliated dispersion of the clay in the materials, demonstrating that the pre-mixing substances of the system plays an important role in the clay dispersion.

Again, the TEM micrographs were corresponding to viscosity and XRD results higher degree of clay exfoliation in epoxy pre-mixing substances (Fig.8a and b) was observed in compared to diamine pre-mixing substances (Fig.8c and d). This confirms that pre-mixing substances have an effect on the degree of clay exfoliation and the improvement of dispersion of silicate layers in epoxy nanocomposite requires pre-mixing substance in the production process.

3.2 Mechanical property

Fig. 9 shows effect of pre-mixing substances on flexural modulus of epoxy/organoclay nanocomposites. Flexural modulus of epoxy/organoclay nanocomposites with both epoxy and diamine pre-mixing substances was increased due to additional pre-mixing process which obtained exfoliated clay structure in the epoxy matrix. Flexural modulus of nanocomposites with E1, D1, D2 increases 13%, 88%, 67% compared to neat resin, respectively. It implies that clay exfoliated structure would increase flexural modulus.

Fig.9. Effect of pre-mixing substances on flexural modulus of epoxy/organoclay nanocomposites.

Especially, flexural diamine pre-mixing substance significantly increases in comparison with epoxy pre-mixing substance. It would be because of not only improvement in clay exfoliation effect, but also long alkyl group exchange effect which stuffs molecular chain mobility compared to short alkyl group of modified . As a result, the improvement of flexural modulus of epoxy/organoclay nanocomposites is recommended to have organoclay pre-mixing process with diamine pre-mixing substance before mixing with epoxy resin and curing agent.

3.3 Corrosion Behavior

Fig. 10 shows percentage of weight change of neat epoxy and epoxy/organoclay nanocomposite with different pre-mixing substances in term of square root of time. In this study, corrosion in the composite is described by its percentage of weight change in immersed corrosive environment. Percentage of weight saturation of all nanocomposite with pre-mixing substances improvingly decrease compared to neat resin. Typically, percentage of weight saturation of nanocomposite with D2 pre-mixing substance significantly decreases compared to neat resin and nanocomposite with the other pre-mixing substances. It is due to high degree of clay exfoliation in epoxy matrix.

Fig. 10. Percentage of weight change of neat epoxy and epoxy/organoclay nanocomposite with different pre-mixing substances in term of square root of time.

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Fig. 11. Mechanism of clay exfoliation with a) epoxy and b) diamine exfoliators in epoxy matrix

One curious discussion is that epoxy/organoclay nanocomposite with epoxy different pre-mixing substance do not show much improvement on decreasing percentage of weight change as expected. The reason would be that there are two effects on the nanocomposites. Firstly, effect from clay exfoliation which decreases percentage of weight saturation. Secondly, effect from free volume which increases percentage of weight saturation because epoxy functional group of pre-mixing substance reacts with modified surface amine. It will be discuss more in next part, clay exfoliation mechanism.

However, in case of diamine pre-mixing substance, short alkyl group of modified amine of organoclay would exchange with long molecular chain of diamine pre-mixing substance which make longer structure and stronger epoxy matrix.

As a result, corrosion behavior could be improved by adding appropriated pre-mixing substance which is recommended to use long molecular chain of diamine pre-mixing substance.

3.4 Clay Exfoliation Mechanisms

The clay exfoliation mechanisms are proposed in Fig.11. Initially, the penetration of adoptable pre-mixing substance between clay layers has taken place. Adoptable pre-mixing substances are called “Exfoliators” in here, which assist to achieve clay exfoliation structure.

Fig. 11a shows mechanism of clay exfoliation with epoxy exfoliator in epoxy matrix. In case of epoxy functional group of exfoliator requires smaller molecular size than clay interlayer spacing which allows penetrating into clay spacing. Epoxy exfoliator/ modified interlayer amine modifier

reaction starts from clay interlayer and/or the neighborhood. After the reaction, clay interfacial energy would be reduced much lower than non-exfoliator. As these phenomena, clay layers could be much easier to separate from clay gallery to exfoliated layered clay compared to pristine and commercial modified clay. Therefore, individual silicate nanolayers were homogeneously and randomly dispersed throughout epoxy matrix. Unfortunately, during epoxy curing to form the matrix, the clays after pre-mixing process with epoxy exfoliator were not able to bond with main epoxy matrix because epoxy functional group of exfoliator reacts with amine functional group of modified surface clay which occur free volume surrounding layered clays themselves. These phenomena could affect to reduce performance of the nanocomposites.

To focus on mechanical and barrier properties of nanocomposites with pre-mixing process using epoxy exfoliator, they could not achieve to be excellent as expected from extremely high degree of clay exfoliation. It could be because of two main effects occurring while processing the nanocomposites: firstly, improving effect from clay exfoliation. These exfoliated clay fix the matrix molecular chain and in consequence mass uptake is decreased in the polymer matrix and secondly, declining effect from no reaction with main epoxy matrix which makes the free volume.

Mechanism of clay exfoliation with diamine exfoliator in epoxy matrix is illustrated in Fig.11b. In case of diamine functional group of exfoliator requires long molecular which would exchange its long alkyl group of the exfoliator with short alkyl group of amine interlayer modifier during pre-mixing process. These phenomena would enhance to enlarge interfacial clay spacing, and hence, exfoliated clay structure in epoxy matrix was produced. Moreover, exchanged long amine alkyl group from diamine exfoliator on layered clays are able to bond with main epoxy matrix which is one of the key factors to improve properties of nanocomposites.

As expected, mechanical and barrier properties of nanocomposites with pre-mixing process using diamine exfoliator obtains high value. Noticeably, improving effects of the nanocomposites with diamine exfoliator is clay exfoliation which is homogenous and rigid structure between nanoclay

and epoxy matrix which bond together.

So, it is noticed that small molecular structure of epoxy and long molecular structure of diamine exfoliator would be one of the key parameters to achieve clay exfoliation on epoxy matrix. To improve flexural modulus and corrosion resistance, it is recommended to employ long molecular structure of diamine exfoliator in pre-mixing process because organoclays after pre-mixing with the exfoliator are still able to bond with the main epoxy matrix.

4 Conclusions

Fully epoxy/organoclay nanocomposites have been obtained with clay exfoliators. Epoxy reactive diluents and diamine curing agents pre-mixing substances play an important role on clay exfoliation into epoxy matrix as clay exfoliators. Pre-mixing process with epoxy and diamine exfoliators assists to obtain fully exfoliated epoxy/clay nanocomposites confirming from all viscosity, XRD and TEM micrographs. Epoxy exfoliator has more effected on increasing degree of clay exfoliation compared to diamine exfoliator. Flexural modulus and diffusivity of epoxy/ organoclay nanocomposites with diamine exfoliator obtains significantly improving, however, with epoxy exfoliator is not much improving. On these results, the developments of properties for the epoxy/organoclay nanocomposites are now planning.

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References

- [1] A. Usuki, M. Kawasumi, Y. Kojima, A. Okada, T. Kurauchi, and O. Kamigaito "Swelling behavior of montmorillonite cation exchanged for ω -amino acids by ϵ -caprolactam". *Journal of Materials Research*, Vol. 8, No. 5, pp. 1174–1178, 1993.
- [2] A. Okada and A. Usuki "The chemistry of polymer-clay hybrids". *Materials Science and Engineering C*, Vol. 3, No. 2, pp. 109–115, 1995.

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- [3] Unitika Ltd Hiromu Fuji, Katsumi Kuratani, Kazuyuki Wakamura, Masaaki Yamazaki, Polyamide resin composition, EP1022313 A1, *Europe Patent Office*, 26/07/2000.
- [4] Y. Kojima, A. Usuki, M. Kawasumi, A. Okada, Y. Fukushima, T. Kurauchi and O. Kamigaito, "Mechanical properties of nylon 6-clay hybrid". *Journal of Materials Research*, Vol. 8, No.2, pp. 1185-1189, 1993.
- [5] Y. Kojima, A. Usuki, M. Kawasumi, A. Okada, T. Kurauchi and O. Kamigaito, "Sorptions of water in nylon 6-clay hybrid". *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, Vol. 49, No. 7, pp. 1259-1264, 1993.
- [6] K. Yano, A. Usuki, and A. Okada "Synthesis and properties of polyimide-clay hybrid films". *Journal of Polymer Science A*, Vol. 35, No. 11, pp. 2289-2294, 1997.
- [7] A. Esfandiari HN, R. Abo-Saeed Rashidi, Y. Mohamad-Esmaeel "Review of polymer-organoclay nanocomposites". *Journal of Applied Sciences*, Vol. 8, No. 3, pp. 545-561, 2008.
- [8] LA Goettler, Lee KY Thakkar H, "Layered silicate reinforced polymer nanocomposites: development and applications". *Polymer Reviews*, Vol. 47, No. 2, pp. 291-317, 2007.
- [9] M. Zanetti SLGC "Polymer layered silicate nanocomposites". *Macromolecular Materials and Engineering*, Vol. 279, No. 1, pp. 1-9, 2000.
- [10] DR Paul, Robeson LM "Polymer nanotechnology: nanocomposites". *Polymer*, Vol. 49, No.15, pp.3187-3204, 2008.
- [11] T.-D. Ngo, M.-T. Ton-Thata and S.V. Hoa "Effect of temperature, duration and speed of pre-mixing on the dispersion of clay/epoxy nanocomposites". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 69, No. 11-12, pp 1831-1840, 2009.
- [12] N. Abacha, M. Kubouchi T. Sakai and K. Tsuda "Diffusion Behavior of Water and Sulfuric Acid in of Epoxy/Organoclay Nanocomposite". *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, Vol. 112, No. 2, pp 1021-1029, 2009.
- [13] K. Saitoh, K. Ohashi, T. Oyama, A. Takahashi, J. Kadota, H. Hirano and K. Hasegawa "Development of high-performance epoxy/clay nanocomposites by incorporating novel phosphonium modified montmorillonite". *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, Vol.122, No. 1, pp. 666-675, 2011.
- [14] J. Hyun Park and S. C. Jana "Mechanism of Exfoliation of Nanoclay Particles in Epoxy-Clay Nanocomposites". *Macromolecules*, Vol.36, No.8, pp 2758-2768, 2003.
- [15] X. Kornmann, H. Lindberg and L.A. Berglund "Synthesis of epoxy-clay nanocomposites. Influence of the nature of the curing agent on structure". *Polymer*, Vol. 42, No. 10, pp. 4493-4499, 2001.
- [16] X. Kornmann, L. A. Berglund, R. Thomann, R. Mulhaupt, J. Finter "High performance epoxy-layered silicate nanocomposites" *Polymer Engineering & Science*, Vol. 42, No.9, pp. 1815-1826, 2002.
- [17] W. Keyoonwong, M. Kubouchi, T. Sakai, and S. Aoki "Preparation of exfoliated epoxy/clay nanocomposite and its thermal & mechanical properties". *Proceedings of International Symposium on Engineering, Energy and Environment (ISEEE09 '09)*, Rayong, Thailand, pp. 158-163, 2009.
- [18] T. P. Mohan, M. Ramesh Kumar, R. Velmurugan "Thermal, mechanical and vibration characteristics of epoxy-clay nanocomposites". *Journal of Materials Science*, Vol. 41, No.18, pp. 5915-5925, 2006
- [19] W. Keyoonwong, Y. Guo, M. Kubouchi, S.Aoki and T. Sakai "Corrosion behavior of three nanoclay dispersion methods of epoxy/organoclay nanocomposites" *International Journal of Corrosion*, Vol. 2012, pp 1-10, 2012.